

Table 1. Yield and plant ancillary characteristics from varietal yield trial experiments, São Raimundo, Brazil, 1981.^a

Entry	Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Effective tillers/plant	Lodging (%)	Days to flowering	Days to maturity
J-32	IR22	6.78	108	19	1	103	138
J-40	IR24	7.91	98	20	1	93	126
J-179	IR36	7.63	86	27	3	85	116
J-229	P738-97-3-1	7.56	100	20	1	103	136
J-233	Juma 58	6.71	118	18	1	111	145
J-266	IR11248-52-2-3-3	6.59	113	27	7	95	126
J-301	IET6503	6.16	104	25	3	85	118
J-305	IAC899-55-6-4-6	7.84	116	21	1	94	128
J-310	P1291	9.00	123	18	1	104	136
J-311 (Phil.)	BR51-46-1-C-1	7.25	118	20	5	98	130
J-311 (S.P.)	BR51-46-1-C-1	7.50	122	18	1	101	134
J-314	IR665-23-3-1	7.61	106	19	1	98	131
J-319	IET5518 (CR35-2740)	6.79	103	21	1	84	115
J-323	IR9129-7-1	6.38	86	23	1	77	110
J-324	IR9129-102-2	6.55	96	24	1	82	114
J-325	IR9168-13-1	8.00	107	23	1	85	116
J-327	UPR70	5.08	90	22	1	82	113
LSD (0.05)		0.90					
CV (%)		8.90					

^aGermplasm for J-311 (Phil.) was received from the Philippines and J-311 (S.P.) from the Instituto Agrônomico de Campinas, Brazil.

mercial variety. It was compared with J-310, J-311 (S.P.), J-311 (Phil.), J-314, J-325, J-40, J-179, and J-305. Variety J-310 yielded best but had high opacity and broken grain percentage. J-311 (S.P.), which was resistant to leaf blast, needs further testing in large plots. Most J-311 (Phil.) plants lodged. J-314, J-179, and J-324 had a low percentage of whole grains and a high percentage of opacity. J-40 was susceptible to leaf blast and neck blast. J-305 had medium (5.87 mm) grain length. Variety J-266, which gave good results in 1980, yielded low and lodged severely. It had medium grain length. *h*

Table 2. Grain quality and milling yields of different varieties, São Raimundo, Brazil, 1981.

Entry	Milling yield (%)	Whole grains (%)	Opacity (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain width (mm)	L/W ^a ratio
J-32	71.28	61.92	11	6.82	2.44	2.80
J-40	69.44	49.44	13	6.76	2.04	3.31
J-179	72.56	35.44	28	6.43	1.87	3.44
J-229	67.52	46.50	14	6.55	2.12	3.09
J-233	67.20	44.16	32	6.72	2.25	2.99
J-266	71.52	52.90	14	5.88	2.11	2.79
J-301	70.08	46.32	13	6.49	1.77	3.66
J-305	69.92	54.32	12	5.87	2.00	2.94
J-310	72.72	53.04	33	7.17	2.11	3.40
J-311 (Phil.)	72.88	60.80	20	6.60	2.19	3.01
J-311 (S.P.)	70.80	53.60	23	6.50	2.28	2.85
J-314	69.68	39.10	35	7.16	2.00	3.58
J-319	72.56	57.84	17	7.14	2.08	3.43
J-323	72.24	58.64	12	6.40	2.02	3.39
J-324	70.72	44.48	18	6.59	2.05	3.21
J-325	71.28	35.20	38	7.32	2.13	3.44
J-327	66.16	55.84	33	6.87	2.01	3.42

^aLength-width.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Rice panicle type for high grain yields in low temperature areas

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High rice yields result from large numbers of spikelets per unit area.

Number of spikelets depends on panicles per unit area and spikelets per panicle.

In modern varieties planted in the tropics, increased yield is generally pro-

Table 1. 1981 IRCTN entries by grain yield, panicle number per hill, and spikelets per panicle. Chuncheon, Korea, 1981.

Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelets/panicle	Entries (no.) with given panicles/hill				
		4-6	7-9	10-12	13-15	16-18
>6	<130	0	0	10	8	2
	>130	1	5	10	1	0
<6	<130	1	27	32	9	0
	>130	4	29	21	4	0

duced by increasing panicle number (panicle number type). In traditional indica varieties with limited panicle

number at flowering, yield is multiplied by increasing panicle weight or spikelets per panicle (panicle weight type).

In low temperature areas, some farmers prefer panicle weight type rice because panicles are harvested individually. The 1981 International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) planted in Korea was analyzed to determine if high yields result from high panicle number or large spikelet number per panicle.

High yields resulted from high panicle number (10-12/hill) (Table 1). However, both panicle weight and panicle number types can produce large yields. Suweon 306 and IR9129-169-3-2-3-3 yielded high because they had many panicles per hill

Table 2. Grain yield, number of panicles per hill, and number of spikelets per panicle of high yielding IRCTN entries. Chuncheon, Korea, 1981.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Panicle number	Total spikelets	Fertility (%)	Flowering date
TI668	7.16	6.0	196	91	1 Aug
Barkat	6.18	8.2	150	89	28 Jul
IR15924-265-3	8.94	8.2	135	84	18 Aug
IR9224-K1	9.49	13.0	140	95	31 Jul
AC3828	8.63	13.0	127	94	5 Aug
C11561-1	8.05	13.4	112	95	11 Aug
IR9129-169-3-2-3-3	6.18	17.0	124	84	7 Aug
Suweon 306	6.86	18.4	115	76	18 Aug

(Table 2). TI668 and Barkat, from mountain regions, produced large yields from big panicles. IR9224-K1, an IRRI

line reselected in Kashmir, India, has high panicle and spikelet numbers and yielded the highest.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Testing for sheath blight resistance in rice

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Rice sheath blight (ShB), caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn [*Thanetophorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk.], occurs during wet season in parts of Kerala, Andhra Pradesh (A. P.), and West Bengal. In 1979 a severe outbreak occurred on BPT1235 and MTU6024 in West Godavari district, A. P.

Chemical control is the only way to arrest ShB. Resistant short-statured rice varieties need to be developed.

A program to breed high yielding varieties with ShB resistance was initiated

at AICRIP, Hyderabad, during 1979 kharif. Fifty-eight entries were field tested. Plants were inoculated by typhabit method at maximum tillering. Thirty-seven varieties were moderately resistant; scores ranged from 3.0 to 5.0. During 1980 kharif moderately resistant entries were retested in two 3.75-m rows flanked by the susceptible check variety Taichung Native 1. High humidity (RH 95%) created by overhead sprinklers induced maximum disease. Only 11 varieties showed resistant reaction (score 1.0 to 3.0) in high humidity (see table). OS4 and IR42 were scored as resistant, confirming 1979 results. IET4699 was resistant, Guyana sel. 60-283 and Pankaj were moderately resistant.

Eight thousand F₄ plants from three

crosses — RP1821 (OS4/ RPW6-I7), RP1819 (Pankaj/RP1821), and RP1822 (Pankaj/ IET5656) — were field tested under favorable conditions. RP1821 crosses were most promising — 189 plants scored highly resistant (0.0 and 1.0). Among those, 76 lines were uniform. They are being tested in a replicated yield trial at AICRIP headquarters during the 1982 dry season and at Maruteru, West Godavari, reported to be a ShB hot spot, to reconfirm disease reaction.

Tetep: a potential source of resistance to rice dwarf in Nepal

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In 1977 rice dwarf virus (RD) was discovered in Taichung 176 and KT32-2 (a locally bred line) at Khumaltar Station in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. *Nephotetix nigropictus*, the predominant green leafhopper species in the valley, transmits the virus. To identify potential sources of RD resistance, a preliminary screening of rice cultivars was made in the greenhouse at Khumaltar during July-September 1981. We sought to

Donor screening nursery results at AICRIP, 1980 kharif.

Entries with score ^a of					
0	1	3	5	7	9
	ET4699	IR2071-588-4		IET6774	TN1
		Guyana Sel. 60-283		RP193-1	Ram Tulse
		ET5891	T141	ARC15762	
		ET6770	Ta-poo-cho-z	IR2071-588-5	
		Pankaj	IET6234	La ka	
		IR42	IR1103-15-8		
		OS4	Nang Payah		
		ET6235	Ramadja	Phourel	
		IET6272	IET7043	Morangedo	
		Saibham	IET7109	Phekaudu	
			Athebu	Morang Chaeran	
			Mamte	Bag Murali	
			Suduwee		

^a 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves and some plants killed.